

Unstable Evidence, Stable Conclusion: A Critique of the GDP Overestimation Thesis of Anand, Felman, and Subramanian (2026)

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Abstract

The Peterson Institute working paper by [Anand et al. \(2026\)](#) claims that Indian GDP growth has been overestimated by 1.5 to 1.9 percentage points per year over 2011 to 2023, with an implied level overstatement of 22 percent as of 2025. The paper is a direct continuation of the thesis advanced in [Subramanian \(2019\)](#), a Harvard working paper in which Subramanian, a co-author on the 2026 paper, argued the same position seven years earlier. This paper establishes that the magnitude claim is not supported by the evidence presented. The 2019 paper's central empirical finding, that correlations between macro indicators and GDP broke down after 2011, does not survive extension of the data window to 2024; of the eleven indicators flagged as negatively correlated with GDP, ten have reversed to positive, including IIP Manufacturing, which has moved from -0.78 to $+0.92$. The informal sector's contribution of 0.4 to 0.8 percentage points rests on a compound growth rate computed across incompatible surveys—UNES (2010–11) and ASUSE (2023–24)—spanning 13 years. The sales-GVA wedge presented as independent evidence is partly mechanical, driven by the paper's asymmetric deflator choices. None of the five correlation changes in the paper's Figure 2 reaches statistical significance under the Fisher r-to-z test, and the cross-country regression's India dummy falls by 24 percent when two excluded observations are added back. Five specific positions from the 2019 paper are reversed in the 2026 paper without acknowledgment. The paper's own tax appendix documents surging economic activity in sectors that should register in measured GDP, then characterises this as compositional rather than as growth. Across seven years and two papers, the headline claim has remained stable within a narrow decimal band while the indicators, mechanisms, and magnitude supporting it have been rebuilt. The pattern is consistent with a conclusion held fixed while evidence is replaced.

JEL Codes: E01, O47, C82, O11, O53

Keywords: GDP mismeasurement; national accounts; informal sector; price deflators; statistical inference; India

1 Introduction

The measurement of Indian gross domestic product has been the subject of sustained debate since the 2015 methodological revision introduced by the Central Statistical Office. [Subramanian \(2019\)](#), writing as sole author in a Harvard working paper, argued that the new methodology had led to an overestimation of approximately 2.5 percentage points per year over 2011 to 2016, with a 95 percent confidence interval of plus-or-minus 1 percentage point. [Anand et al. \(2026\)](#) return to the same thesis with extended data and revised mechanisms, claiming an overestimation of 1.5 to 1.9 percentage points per year over 2011 to 2023 and a cumulative level overstatement of approximately 22 percent as of 2025. The 2026 paper has received substantial media and policy attention.

Subramanian, sole author of the 2019 paper, is a co-author on the 2026 paper. Felman, also a co-author of the 2026 paper, was acknowledged in the 2019 paper’s front matter as having “first alerted me to the issues, and for helping at every stage” ([Subramanian, 2019](#), p. 1). Two of the three 2026 authors have therefore been associated with this research program since before 2019. This paper examines whether the evidence now offered in support of the same thesis holds.

It does not. Six findings establish that the 2026 paper’s magnitude claim of 1.5 to 1.9 percentage points is not supported by the evidence the paper presents.

1. **Indicator selection** (Section 2). Of the seventeen macro indicators used in the 2019 paper, thirteen are absent from the 2026 paper. On the extended 2012 to 2024 window, ten of the eleven indicators flagged by the 2019 paper as negatively correlated with GDP show positive correlation. IIP Manufacturing, on which the 2019 paper rested much of its manufacturing-sector argument, now correlates with GDP at 0.92.
2. **Survey incomparability** (Section 3). The informal sector contribution of 0.4 to 0.8 percentage points is computed as a compound annual growth rate between UNES (2010 to 2011) and ASUSE (2023 to 2024), separated by thirteen years and by a change in survey instrument, sampling frame, and coverage.
3. **Deflator circularity and the abandonment of double deflation** (Section 4). The paper deflates corporate sales by CPI core while GVA is deflated substantially by WPI; the resulting sales-GVA wedge correlates with the CPI-WPI gap at 0.81, and a portion of this correlation is generated mechanically by the deflator divergence. Although CPI core is a more defensible deflator than headline CPI for corporate sales, the wedge between any consumer-price-based deflator and a wholesale-price-based deflator contributes to the observed divergence by construction. The paper also reverses the 2019 paper’s core double-deflation mechanism without acknowledgment.
4. **Statistical insignificance** (Section 4.4). None of the five correlation changes in the paper’s Figure 2 reaches statistical significance under the Fisher r-to-z test. The cross-country regression’s India dummy falls by 24 percent when two excluded observations are added back.

5. **Author self-contradiction** (Section 6). Five specific positions from the 2019 paper are reversed in the 2026 paper without acknowledgment. The 2026 magnitude range sits entirely within the lower half of the 2019 paper’s 95 percent confidence interval.
6. **Tax revenue evidence** (Section 7). Post-2020 tax performance creates an unresolved tension with the overestimation thesis. The paper’s Appendix C attributes the tax boom to composition effects (income concentration, luxury consumption, GCC expansion) rather than aggregate growth, but the activities generating the tax revenue are themselves components of GDP. The paper does not reconcile the strong performance of taxable economic activity with its claim that aggregate growth was overstated.

Each finding is independently verifiable against the 2019 and 2026 papers and against public data sources.

Section 2 through Section 7 develop each of the six findings in turn. Section 8 synthesises what the cumulative evidence implies for the 2026 paper’s magnitude claim. Five appendices provide the direct quotations from both papers supporting the self-contradiction argument, the full correlation data, a note on window sensitivity, and the supporting indicator and correlation figures.

2 Indicator Selection: The Vanishing Thirteen

2.1 The two indicator sets

The 2019 paper’s correlation evidence rests on seventeen real-economy indicators, chosen, in the paper’s own words, because they are “strongly correlated with GDP growth” and “produced independently of the CSO” (Subramanian, 2019, p. 6). The paper’s Figure 1 presents the correlation of each indicator with GDP growth over 2001 to 2011 on one axis and over 2012 to 2017 on the other, and reports the headline finding:

“16 out of 17 indicators are positively correlated with GDP growth before 2011... However, post-2011, 11 out of 17 indicators are negatively correlated with GDP.”
(Subramanian, 2019, p. 7)

This was the central evidence of the 2019 paper. The visual pattern in Figure 1, a cloud of indicators below the horizontal zero line in the post-2011 period, was presented as the finding that the 2015 methodology had broken the signal between real economic activity and GDP.

The 2026 paper uses six indicators: exports, bank credit, IIP, electricity, direct tax, and corporate sales (Anand et al., 2026, p. 4). Four overlap with the 2019 set. Thirteen indicators are absent. Two indicators are new. Table 1 presents the two sets and their overlap.

Among the thirteen indicators dropped between the 2019 and 2026 analyses, the most consequential is IIP Manufacturing. Section V of the 2019 paper devoted pages 19 through 24 to the

Table 1: Indicator sets used in Subramanian (2019) and Anand, Felman, and Subramanian (2026)

Indicator	In 2019 set	In 2026 set	Status
Exports of goods and services	Yes	Yes	Retained
Bank credit (overall)	Yes	Yes	Retained
IIP (overall)	Yes	Yes	Retained
Electricity consumption	Yes	Yes	Retained
IIP Manufacturing	Yes	No	Dropped
IIP Consumer goods	Yes	No	Dropped
Cement	Yes	No	Dropped
Steel	Yes	No	Dropped
Petroleum consumption	Yes	No	Dropped
Airline passenger traffic	Yes	No	Dropped
2-wheeler sales	Yes	No	Dropped
Commercial vehicle sales	Yes	No	Dropped
Tractor sales	Yes	No	Dropped
Foreign tourist arrivals	Yes	No	Dropped
Railway freight traffic	Yes	No	Dropped
Imports of goods and services	Yes	No	Dropped
Real credit to industry	Yes	No	Dropped
Direct tax revenues	No	Yes	Added
Corporate sales	No	Yes	Added

claim that the correlation between IIP Manufacturing growth and formal manufacturing GVA growth had turned negative after 2011. The paper described the result as “bizarre” and used the IIP-GVA manufacturing divergence as the empirical input to its argument that formal manufacturing mismeasurement accounts for a substantial portion of the claimed overestimation, roughly on the order of 1 percentage point of annual GDP growth (Subramanian, 2019, p. 22). The formal manufacturing channel is therefore a sizeable component of the 2019 paper’s total 2.5 pp claim. The 2026 paper retains IIP at the aggregate level but drops the manufacturing sub-component.

2.2 The claim does not survive on the author’s own chart structure

The cleanest test of whether the 2019 empirical claim holds on extended data is to reconstruct Figure 1 of the 2019 paper with the post-period extended by seven years. Figure 1 presents the original 2019 chart (Panel A) and the reconstruction using 2012 to 2024 data (Panel B). The structure of the two panels is identical. Only the length of the post-2011 window differs: 2012 to 2017 in the 2019 paper, 2012 to 2024 on extended data. In both panels, the x-axis shows correlation with GDP growth over 2001 to 2011; the y-axis shows correlation with GDP growth over the post-2011 period. The 45-degree line represents stable correlations across the two periods; the horizontal axis at zero separates positive from negative post-2011 correlations.

Panel A is the 2019 paper’s own evidence. Eleven of seventeen indicators fall below the horizontal zero line, meaning they correlate negatively with GDP over 2012 to 2017. The visual cloud in the lower half of the panel is what the 2019 paper called the “bizarre” departure of real-economy indicators from measured GDP.

Figure 1: Correlations between selected real-economy indicators and GDP growth, pre-2011 (2001 to 2011, x-axis) versus post-2011 (y-axis). Panel A reproduces Figure 1 of Subramanian (2019) with the post-period running 2012 to 2017, showing 11 of 17 indicators below the horizontal zero line and therefore negatively correlated with GDP in the post-methodology period. Panel B applies the same structure with the post-period extended to 2012 to 2024. Panel B correlations are computed using publicly available data (sources listed in Appendix B); Panel A values are as published. Only Tractor remains below the zero line in Panel B. The indicator-breakdown finding that motivated the 2019 paper’s central claim does not survive extension of the post-period from 2012–2017 to 2012–2024.

Panel B applies the identical analytical structure, extending the post-period from 2012 to 2017 out to 2012 to 2024. Sixteen of seventeen indicators now correlate positively with GDP. Only Tractor remains below the zero line, and Tractor tracks monsoon cycles, minimum support price announcements, and rural credit rather than aggregate GDP. In some of its key comparisons (particularly those involving corporate sales), the 2026 paper excludes agriculture and public administration from GVA, which makes Tractor an inappropriate indicator for testing the overestimation thesis in any case.

The 2019 paper’s central empirical finding therefore does not hold on extended data. The indicators the paper flagged as “bizarrely” decoupled from GDP after 2011 were responding to the concentrated real-economy shocks of 2016 through 2019: demonetization, GST implementation, the NBFC crisis, and their interaction. Once the post-period window extends past those shocks, the correlations return to the positive range consistent with indicators of aggregate activity. The 2019 paper’s claim that the 2015 methodology had broken the signal does not survive extension of the window and therefore cannot be treated as robust evidence of a structural break.

A further consideration strengthens this conclusion. The 2001 to 2011 correlations used on the x-axis of Figure 1 were estimated on an Indian economy with a different structural composition than the 2012 to 2024 economy on the y-axis. Oil intensity of output has fallen. Logistics costs as a share of GDP are widely cited as having declined materially over the period. The services share of GVA has risen above 55 percent (MoSPI National Accounts Statistics). Digital payments and GST-driven formalization have changed the visibility of transactions. Several of the indicators plotted (petroleum, freight, 2-wheelers, commercial vehicles) have elasticities with respect to aggregate GDP that are unlikely to be constant across this transformation. Even if the methodology had been identical across both periods, indicator-GDP correlations would be expected to shift. The AFS framework does not distinguish shifts driven by structural change from shifts driven by methodology. Section 8 develops this specification problem.

2.3 The specific correlations Subramanian reported have reversed

Table 2 reports the specific correlations from the 2019 paper’s Figure 1 (read against the paper’s published chart) alongside correlations computed on the extended 2012 to 2024 window. Updated correlations are computed using publicly available data (sources listed in Appendix B) and replicate the structure of the 2019 paper’s original figure; they are not taken from the 2019 paper or from any other secondary source.

One technical clarification applies specifically to IIP Manufacturing. The 2019 paper’s headline “bizarre” claim (Section V, p. 20) concerns the correlation between IIP Manufacturing growth and *formal manufacturing GVA* growth, while the updated correlations reported here and in Appendix B use IIP Manufacturing as a proxy for aggregate activity and report its correlation with *aggregate GDP*. These two correlations are closely related (since formal manufacturing GVA is a component of aggregate GDP) but not identical. The point the updated evidence establishes is that IIP Manufacturing, on extended data, tracks aggregate activity positively and strongly; it does not directly refute the narrower 2019 claim about IIP Manufacturing

versus formal manufacturing GVA specifically. A complete refutation of that narrower claim would require the disaggregated formal manufacturing GVA series, which is not published in a readily verifiable form. The broader claim the 2019 paper drew from its finding (that the 2015 methodology had broken the signal between real activity and measured GDP) is refuted by the aggregate-GDP evidence reported here.

Table 2: Correlations with GDP: 2012 to 2017 (per Subramanian 2019) vs 2012 to 2024 (updated)

Indicator	2012–2017	2012–2024	Direction
IIP Manufacturing	−0.78	+0.92	Reversed
IIP Consumer goods	−0.71	+0.82	Reversed
IIP-GVA Manufacturing	−0.15	+0.44	Reversed
Exports GS	−0.86	+0.52	Reversed
Imports GS	−0.36	+0.61	Reversed
Cement	−0.38	+0.76	Reversed
Steel	−0.32	+0.50	Reversed
Railway Freight	−0.13	+0.37	Reversed
2-Wheeler sales	−0.05	+0.63	Reversed
Credit (Industry)	−0.48	+0.27	Reversed
Credit (real)	+0.03	+0.51	Strengthened
Foreign Tourist	+0.28	+0.50	Strengthened
Petroleum	+0.56	+0.81	Strengthened
IIP (Overall)	+0.16	+0.93	Strengthened
Electricity	+0.55	+0.87	Strengthened
Commercial Vehicles	+0.69	+0.55	Stable
Airlines	+0.88	+0.82	Stable
Tractor	−0.21	−0.38	Remained negative

Note on the 2012–2017 column. The 2019 paper publishes only a scatter chart (Figure 1), not a numerical correlation table; values shown are the analyst’s reading of that chart, cross-checked against independent recomputation on the underlying 2012–2017 data (sources as in Appendix B). For most indicators, the two methods agree closely. For two indicators (Electricity, Railway Freight), chart read-off and independent recomputation differ by more than 0.10 in magnitude; in those cases, the chart read-off is retained as the more faithful representation of the 2019 paper’s own reported evidence. Signs are preserved across all indicators under both methods, so the directional finding on which this section rests does not depend on the eyeball-versus-recomputation choice.

Note on indicator count. The 2019 paper’s text describes its evidence as “16 out of 17” indicators positively correlated pre-2011 and “11 out of 17” negatively correlated post-2011 (Subramanian, 2019, p. 7). The paper’s Figure 1 plots eighteen distinct points. The discrepancy between text count (17) and chart count (18) is not explained in the 2019 paper. Table 2 follows the chart count of 18; narrative references to “11 of 17” or “16 of 17” follow the 2019 paper’s text wording.

Of the eleven indicators the 2019 paper flagged as negatively correlated with GDP, ten have reversed to positive correlation on the extended window. Only Tractor remains negative, a pattern driven by agricultural cycle dynamics. Correlations that ranged from -0.05 to -0.86 on 2012 to 2017 data now sit in the range $+0.27$ to $+0.92$: the indicators have moved approximately one to two correlation units in the opposite direction. IIP Manufacturing, the anchor of the

2019 paper's Section V derivation, has moved from -0.78 to $+0.92$, a shift of 1.70 correlation units.

The 2026 paper does not report these updated correlations. It does not note that the 2019 empirical claim has failed to replicate. It does not attribute any portion of its reduced magnitude estimate (2.5 pp in 2019, 1.5 to 1.9 pp in 2026) to the collapse of the indicator-breakdown evidence. The indicators simply disappear from the analysis.

2.4 Indicators added in 2026

Two indicators in the 2026 paper were not in the 2019 set.

Direct tax revenues. The 2019 paper excluded tax indicators on the ground that structural changes (GST introduction, corporate tax reform) rendered the tax-to-GDP relationship “different and unstable” and therefore “unreliable proxies for GDP growth” (Subramanian, 2019, p. 6). The 2026 paper uses direct tax as one of six headline macro indicators without addressing this prior position. Section 7 addresses the tax argument in full.

Corporate sales. A new construction. The 2026 paper deflates nominal corporate sales by CPI core to produce a “real sales growth” series, and compares this series against official real GVA growth. The wedge between the two is interpreted as evidence of overstatement. Section 4 establishes that the wedge is partly an accounting consequence of the deflator choice.

2.5 The pattern of selection

Among the thirteen indicators dropped between 2019 and 2026, seven show correlations above $+0.60$ with GDP on the extended 2012 to 2024 window. These are not marginal indicators whose removal might be defended on analytical grounds. They are the indicators whose behaviour on extended data directly contradicts the 2019 empirical claim. Their removal from the 2026 analysis leaves the reader unable to observe what the original evidence now shows.

The two indicators added to the 2026 analysis are ones the 2019 paper either rejected as unsuitable (direct tax) or did not use (corporate sales). The added indicator whose wedge against GVA serves as headline evidence (corporate sales) depends for that wedge on a deflator choice (CPI core) that the 2026 paper selects and that partly generates the finding mechanically through deflator asymmetry.

The indicator set between 2019 and 2026 has therefore been restructured in one direction: indicators whose updated behaviour contradicts the thesis are removed, and indicators whose inclusion supports the thesis are added. This is indicator selection filtered to preserve the conclusion.

3 Survey Incomparability: An Unmeasurable Informal Sector Gap

3.1 The paper's informal sector claim

The 2026 paper argues that the Indian informal sector, which it estimates at approximately 44 percent of GVA (Anand et al., 2026, p. 10 and Figure 6), grew substantially slower than the formal sector after 2015, and that official GDP estimation missed this divergence by continuing to proxy informal activity through formal-sector indicators.

The quantitative claim is specific. Per Figure 7 of the paper, annual nominal revenue growth in the formal sector averaged approximately 13 percent over 2010 to 2015 and 10.0 percent over 2015 to 2023. Informal sector revenue grew at 13.0 percent over 2010 to 2015 and at 6.8 percent over 2015 to 2023. The post-2015 gap between the two is approximately 3.3 percentage points (10.0 minus 6.8), and both sides slow relative to the pre-2015 period. The 2026 paper translates the 3.3 percentage point gap, through Figure 14, into an informal GVA overestimation of 0.4 to 0.8 percentage points. This is approximately a quarter to a half of the paper's headline overestimation range of 1.5 to 1.9 percentage points.

The measurement uses three data points:

- NSS 67th Round (UNES 2010 to 2011), for the start of the first period;
- NSS 73rd Round (2015 to 2016), endpoint of the first period and start of the second;
- ASUSE 2023 to 2024, endpoint of the second period.

The overestimation claim in Figure 14 of the paper is anchored by a compound annual growth rate computed between UNES (2010 to 2011) and ASUSE (2023 to 2024), spanning thirteen years.

3.2 The two endpoints are not comparable

UNES 2010 to 2011 and NSS 73rd Round 2015 to 2016 are both NSS Surveys on Unincorporated Non-Agricultural Enterprises. They share broadly similar instrument design, sampling methodology, and enumeration approach. The sampling frame was updated between them (NSS 67th used the 2005 Economic Census; NSS 73rd used the 2013 Economic Census), but the surveys remain reasonably comparable at the aggregate level. A growth rate computed between these two rounds is defensible.

ASUSE is a different exercise. The Annual Survey of Unincorporated Sector Enterprises was launched in 2021 to 2022 as a new annual survey, not a round of the NSS. It uses a redesigned instrument, a different sampling frame construction process (no new Economic Census is available; the attempted 2019 Economic Census was never released), and partially different coverage. The three ASUSE waves conducted to date (2021 to 2022, 2022 to 2023, 2023 to 2024) have themselves undergone methodological refinements between waves.

The differences between the NSS rounds and ASUSE that affect growth rate comparison include:

1. Different sampling frames. NSS rounds relied on Economic Census frames. ASUSE constructs its frame through a different approach. The blow-up factors from sample to population differ accordingly.
2. Different instrument design. ASUSE was redesigned in response to critiques of the earlier NSS rounds, particularly on the treatment of own-account enterprises and home-based workers.
3. Different operational definitions of unincorporated enterprises. ASUSE uses updated definitions that do not align precisely with the NSS rounds.
4. Different reference periods. Treatment of “current activity” and “usual activity” has varied.

A compound annual growth rate computed between UNES (2010 to 2011) and ASUSE (2023 to 2024) therefore conflates economic change with methodology change. The informal sector growth figure that anchors the 2026 paper’s overestimation claim in Figure 14 is not a directly measured growth rate. It is the compound rate implied by two non-identical measurement exercises, divided by thirteen.

3.3 The data gap

Between UNES (2010 to 2011) and ASUSE (2023 to 2024), the only intermediate reading is the NSS 73rd Round (2015 to 2016). The thirteen-year span flies blind through demonetization (November 2016), GST rollout (July 2017), the NBFC crisis (2018 to 2019), the Covid shock (2020), and the initial post-Covid period (2021 to 2022). Five discrete economic shocks occur inside the measurement window. Between the NSS 73rd Round and the first ASUSE wave (2021 to 2022), a gap of six years, no comparable enterprise survey exists at all.

A 13-year CAGR forces all of this variation into a single compound growth rate. Two readings of the same endpoint data are observationally equivalent: the informal sector grew steadily at a below-formal rate for thirteen years, or the informal sector tracked the formal sector until 2015, contracted sharply during 2016 to 2020 under the sequence of shocks, and partially recovered by 2023. The paper adopts the first reading and builds its overestimation contribution on it. The data do not license the choice. A CAGR between two endpoints across a multi-shock interval cannot distinguish chronic underperformance from shock-and-recovery. The 2026 paper does not acknowledge this.

3.4 Partial coverage and the assumption-range substitution

The paper acknowledges (in the note to Figure 7) that the informal sector surveys exclude construction and financial services, and that these sectors are therefore excluded from both sides of the formal-informal comparison. Construction is approximately 76 percent informal per Figure 6 of the paper. Excluding it removes roughly a quarter of the informal economy from the measurement.

The paper addresses this by producing two estimates: an upper bound assuming unmeasured sectors behaved normally, and a lower bound assuming they behaved like the surveyed sectors. The resulting 0.4 to 0.8 percentage point range is presented as a measurement range. It is not. It is the distance between two assumption choices layered on top of non-comparable surveys. A measurement range communicates sampling uncertainty around a point estimate. The 2026 paper's range communicates the modeller's uncertainty about which assumption to apply to sectors the data do not cover. These are different quantities. Presenting the second as the first overstates the precision of the underlying evidence.

3.5 What the measurement cannot establish

The 2026 paper's 0.4 to 0.8 percentage point informal sector contribution to overestimation rests on three operations that the data do not support: a growth rate computed across non-comparable surveys (UNES and ASUSE) spanning thirteen years, a CAGR across a multi-shock interval with only one intermediate observation, and an assumption range for sectors not measured. Each operation alone would weaken the magnitude claim. Combined, they mean the 3.3 percentage point formal-informal gap and the overestimation contribution derived from it are not extractable from the data the paper uses.

The paper presents this contribution as a quantified channel accounting for a quarter to a half of the headline overestimation. The surveys on which the channel rests cannot support a point estimate of that precision. The 0.4 to 0.8 pp figure is not a measurement. It is a construction.

4 Deflator Circularity and the Abandonment of Double Deflation

The 2026 paper's deflator argument has two components. The first is a new empirical finding: a sales-GVA wedge constructed by deflating corporate sales by CPI core while GVA is deflated substantially by WPI, presented as independent evidence of overstatement. The second is a revised mechanism claim: that the 2015 methodology's failure lies in deflator choice rather than in the absence of double deflation. Both components fail under examination. The empirical finding is an artifact of the deflator selection the paper itself makes. The revised mechanism claim contradicts the central technical demonstration of the 2019 paper without acknowledgment.

4.1 The sales-GVA wedge is partly an artifact of construction

The 2026 paper deflates nominal corporate sales by CPI core (that is, CPI excluding food and fuel) to produce a "real sales growth" series. This series is compared against official real GVA growth, which is deflated substantially by WPI-based indices. The resulting sales-GVA wedge is presented as independent evidence of GDP overstatement. Figure 10a of the paper reports a correlation of 0.81 between this wedge and the CPI-WPI gap, interpreted as confirmation that deflator issues drive the overestimation.

A portion of the correlation is a consequence of the deflator selection rather than an independent empirical finding. The accounting identity that links the two variables is:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Real GVA growth} - \text{Real sales growth} &= (\text{Nominal GVA growth} - \text{Nominal sales growth}) \\ &+ (\text{CPI core inflation} - \text{WPI-weighted deflator inflation}) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The second term on the right-hand side approximates the CPI core–WPI gap. The left-hand side is the sales-GVA wedge. The two variables are therefore partly linked by construction. If nominal sales and nominal GVA grew at similar rates (which they broadly do over 2011 to 2024), the first term on the right-hand side is small, and the sales-GVA wedge reduces in part to the CPI core–WPI gap. Note that the x-axis of AFS Figure 10a plots headline CPI minus WPI, not CPI core minus WPI; since CPI core inflation runs below headline CPI inflation, the mechanical component attributable to the deflator choice the paper actually makes (CPI core on the sales side) is smaller than the headline CPI-WPI gap would suggest, though it remains positive.

The magnitude of the mechanically induced wedge depends on the CPI core–WPI differential rather than the headline CPI-WPI gap. Over 2011 to 2024, headline CPI inflation averaged approximately 2.2 percentage points higher than WPI inflation annually (Anand et al., 2026, Figure 9). CPI core inflation, which excludes food and fuel, ran lower than headline CPI over most of this period. The mechanical wedge attributable to the deflator choice is therefore smaller than 2.2 percentage points per year but not zero. A portion of the sales-GVA divergence the 2026 paper presents as evidence of overstatement is an artifact of applying a consumer-price deflator to the sales side and a wholesale-price deflator to the GVA side.

A fair test of whether GDP is mismeasured through deflator choice would require applying the same deflator to both sides of the comparison, or applying deflators matched to the actual composition of the series being deflated. The 2026 paper does neither. It deflates sales by a consumer-price index (CPI core), deflates GVA by a wholesale-price-weighted index, and reports the resulting gap as evidence. However, the quantitative contribution of this mechanical component to the reported wedge is smaller than it would be under headline CPI deflation.

4.2 CPI core as a deflator for corporate sales

The 2026 paper deflates corporate sales by CPI core, which excludes food and beverages and fuel and light from headline CPI. This is a more defensible choice than headline CPI, as it removes the approximately 46 percent food weight that has no meaningful counterpart in corporate output. The critique that follows therefore addresses CPI core specifically, not headline CPI.

CPI core remains a consumer-price index. It measures prices paid by households for a basket of consumption goods and services: housing (imputed rent), clothing, transport, health, education, and miscellaneous personal services. Indian corporate sales, by contrast, consist substantially

of business-to-business transactions that CPI core does not measure at all: steel and cement sold to construction firms, chemicals sold to downstream manufacturers, IT services exported to foreign clients, capital goods sold to industry, pharmaceutical intermediates, and logistics services sold to other corporates. These categories collectively account for a large share of listed corporate revenue. CPI core contains no price information on any of them.

CPI core also includes housing, measured through imputed rent, which has no counterpart in corporate sales for the vast majority of firms. Housing carries a substantial weight in the re-normalised CPI core basket and introduces price dynamics (urban rental inflation) that are unrelated to the prices at which corporates transact.

The appropriate deflator for corporate sales would be a Producer Price Index (PPI) weighted to match the output composition of the corporate sector. India does not yet publish a comprehensive PPI. In its absence, neither CPI core nor WPI provides an adequate match. WPI aligns more closely with the goods component of corporate sales (manufactured products, primary articles, fuel) but does not cover services. CPI core captures some service-sector price movements but measures them from the consumer side rather than the producer side, and misses the business-to-business and export components entirely.

The choice of CPI core for the sales side and WPI-based indices for the GVA side creates a mechanical wedge whenever CPI core inflation diverges from WPI inflation. Over 2011 to 2024, CPI core inflation systematically exceeded WPI inflation, though by a narrower margin than the headline CPI-WPI gap of approximately 2.2 percentage points cited in the 2026 paper's Figure 9. Had the paper applied the same deflator to both sides of the comparison, a portion of the reported sales-GVA wedge would not arise. The paper does not isolate how much of the wedge reflects genuine mismeasurement of real activity versus how much reflects the residual deflator asymmetry.

4.3 The double deflation reversal

The deflator argument in the 2026 paper is the replacement for a different argument in the 2019 paper. In 2019, the core mechanism offered for GDP overestimation in the formal manufacturing sector was the absence of double deflation. Subramanian (2019), writing as sole author, was explicit:

“Ideally, if output values are deflated by output prices and input values by input prices (what is called ‘double deflation’), real value added can be properly estimated. But the methodology did not also involve a move to such double deflation; the methodology involved deflating both output and input values by output prices. This immediately induces a bias as the example below shows.” (Subramanian, 2019, p. 19)

Table 3 of the 2019 paper demonstrated the bias numerically. Under single deflation with a constant output price, a fall in input prices produces apparent real growth of 21 percent. Under double deflation applied to the same scenario, real growth is zero. The single-versus-double comparison was the analytical core of the 2019 paper's Section V. The paper used this

mechanism to derive approximately 1 percentage point of the claimed 2.5 pp overestimation, attributed specifically to formal manufacturing (Subramanian, 2019, p. 22).

In the 2026 paper, the same author, now as co-author with Anand and Felman, reverses this position:

“To be clear, the main problem with the 2015 series was not the absence of double deflation, as is often alleged. In fact, this was a relatively minor problem. The real problem was the use of inappropriate deflators and inappropriate indicators.” (Anand et al., 2026, p. 3)

“A third alternative goes to the heart of the matter: the use of double deflation with inappropriate deflators. If output and input are deflated separately but input prices are inappropriately applied to both, the overestimation will remain unchanged. . . This result shows that the real problem is not the lack of double deflation. It is inappropriate deflators.” (Anand et al., 2026, p. 14)

Footnote 18 of the 2026 paper adds: “Double deflation per se is not the solution to this problem” (Anand et al., 2026, p. 15).

The 2026 paper constructs a new Table 3 to demonstrate the opposite of what the 2019 Table 3 demonstrated. The 2019 table was constructed to show that double deflation fixes the bias created by single deflation. The 2026 table is constructed to show that double deflation with the wrong deflators does not fix the bias. Both tables carry the same illustrative structure (volume extrapolation, double deflation, single deflation across two periods with a fall in input prices) and the same author’s name. The 2026 paper cites the 2019 paper in its reference list. It does not acknowledge that its central technical demonstration contradicts the central technical demonstration of the earlier work.

The reversal is not a minor clarification. Double deflation was the single most-developed technical mechanism in the 2019 paper and carried roughly on the order of 1 percentage point of the claimed 2.5 pp overestimation. The 2026 paper reduces the overall estimate to 1.5 to 1.9 pp, attributes none of the reduction to the abandonment of double deflation as a mechanism, and does not report what happens to the 2019 estimate when double deflation is conceded to be minor. If the 1 percentage point attributed to double deflation in 2019 is removed and nothing replaces it, the 2019 claim reduces to 1.5 pp, which sits at the lower bound of the 2026 estimate. The reader is not given the arithmetic to perform this reconciliation.

4.4 The combined effect

The deflator argument in the 2026 paper therefore does two things simultaneously. It discards the core mechanism of the 2019 paper and replaces it with a different mechanism, without acknowledging the discard. It then constructs an empirical test of the new mechanism (the sales-GVA wedge) using a deflator selection (CPI core for sales, WPI-based indices for GVA)

that generates a portion of the finding mechanically through the deflator asymmetry rather than purely through measurement of real activity. The use of CPI core rather than headline CPI narrows the mechanical component relative to what headline CPI deflation would produce, but does not eliminate it.

The 2026 paper materially downgrades the 2019 mechanism, treating what had earlier been presented as a central channel as a relatively minor problem. The 2026 mechanism that replaces it rests partly on evidence that follows from the deflator asymmetry rather than purely from data. The use of CPI core reduces the mechanical component relative to headline CPI, but the paper does not isolate how much of the sales-GVA wedge reflects genuine mismeasurement versus how much reflects the residual deflator divergence. Neither the 2019 nor the 2026 deflator argument fully supports the overestimation magnitude either paper claims.

5 Statistical Insignificance: The Correlation Evidence Cannot Carry the Claim

The 2026 paper's Figure 2 reports five correlations between GVA and macro indicators across two periods, and interprets the differences between period correlations as evidence that the post-2011 methodology has broken the relationship between GDP and real economic activity. This section applies the standard Fisher r-to-z test to those five correlation changes, examines single-observation sensitivity, and considers the implications of serial correlation in the underlying series. The correlation evidence does not reach conventional statistical significance, does not survive one-observation perturbations, and is not precise enough to support the decimal-place magnitude the paper claims. [Singh and Sinha \(2026\)](#) reach parallel conclusions in an April 2026 EAC-PM policy note; where specific numerical results below coincide with theirs, they are cited as independent confirmation of the same calculations.

5.1 Sample sizes and the Fisher test

The 2026 paper reports correlations for two periods: 1995 to 2011 (nominal $n = 17$) and 2012 to 2024 excluding 2020 to 2021 (nominal $n = 11$). To test whether the change in correlation between the two periods is statistically significant, the standard procedure is the Fisher r-to-z transformation:

$$z = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{1+r}{1-r} \right) \quad (2)$$

The standard error of the difference between two transformed correlations is:

$$SE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_1 - 3} + \frac{1}{n_2 - 3}} \quad (3)$$

With $n_1 = 17$ and $n_2 = 11$, $SE = \sqrt{1/14 + 1/8} = 0.443$. A correlation change is significant at the conventional 5 percent level when the z-statistic of the difference exceeds 1.96, which requires an observed difference in transformed correlations of at least $1.96 \times 0.443 = 0.87$ units. In correlation terms, this means the two period correlations must differ by approximately 0.87 or more (at points near zero) for the change to be distinguishable from sampling noise.

Table 3 applies this test to each of the five AFS Figure 2 correlation pairs.

Table 3: Fisher r-to-z test applied to the five correlation changes in AFS Figure 2

Pair	r_1	r_2	Δz	p -value	Sig. at 5%?	Sig. at 10%?
GVA, Exports	+0.40	-0.15	0.5748	0.1947	No	No
GVA, IIP	+0.80	+0.70	0.2313	0.6017	No	No
GVA, Bank Credit	+0.66	+0.42	0.3451	0.4362	No	No
GVA, Direct Tax	+0.70	+0.24	0.6225	0.1601	No	No
GVA, Electricity	+0.70	+0.52	0.291	0.5115	No	No

None of the five correlation changes reaches significance at the 5 percent level. None reaches significance at the 10 percent level. The largest observed change, for GVA-Direct Tax, has a p-value of 0.160. The correlation change that the 2026 paper treats as qualitatively most important, GVA-Exports (moving from +0.40 to -0.15), has a p-value of 0.195. The statistical basis for treating these correlation differences as evidence of anything is absent. [Singh and Sinha \(2026\)](#), Table A.1.4, reports the same p-values under the same test.

5.2 Confidence intervals

The precision of the period 2 correlations themselves is also limited. The 95 percent confidence interval for a Pearson correlation with $n = 11$ observations is wide. For four of the five correlations reported by AFS, the interval includes negative values:

- GVA, Exports ($r = -0.15$): $[-0.69, +0.49]$
- GVA, Bank Credit ($r = +0.42$): $[-0.24, +0.81]$
- GVA, Direct Tax ($r = +0.24$): $[-0.42, +0.73]$
- GVA, Electricity ($r = +0.52$): $[-0.12, +0.85]$

At these bounds, the same 11 observations are statistically compatible with strongly positive, zero, and moderately negative underlying correlations. The point estimates the paper reports are not sharp enough to distinguish one case from another. The paper nonetheless reports these point estimates as qualitative evidence for specific directional claims.

5.3 Single-observation sensitivity

Small samples produce point estimates that depend heavily on individual observations. The AFS correlations exhibit this sensitivity at the one-observation level.

Dropping FY2015 to 2016 alone from Period 2 flips the GVA-Exports correlation from -0.15 to $+0.22$. One observation reverses the sign of the correlation that the 2026 paper uses as its clearest case of post-2011 breakdown.

Adding back the two Covid observations that AFS excludes from Period 2 moves the GVA-Exports correlation to $+0.49$. This is stronger than the Period 1 correlation of $+0.40$ that the paper treats as the undisturbed baseline. Two observations move the result past the baseline in the opposite direction of the paper's claim.

The cross-country regression the paper uses to corroborate the correlation evidence is similarly fragile. The India dummy coefficient of 2.4 percentage points falls to 1.8 percentage points, a reduction of 24 percent, when the two Covid observations are included in the regression sample (reported in [Singh and Sinha, 2026](#), Table A.1.3). The R-squared barely changes, indicating that the reduction is not from improved fit. Two observations move the headline magnitude by a quarter.

A result that reverses sign from one observation, and a headline coefficient that loses a quarter of its magnitude from two observations, do not meet conventional thresholds for robustness.

5.4 The 2019 paper's evidence was more underpowered, not less

The 2026 paper is a continuation of the 2019 paper. The 2019 paper's headline empirical claim, that 11 of 17 indicators turned negatively correlated with GDP after the methodology change, rested on correlations computed on a pre-period of 2001 to 2011 ($n = 11$) and a post-period of 2012 to 2017 ($n = 6$).

Applied to these sample sizes, the Fisher r-to-z standard error is:

$$SE_{2019} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{11-3} + \frac{1}{6-3}} = \sqrt{1/8 + 1/3} = 0.677 \quad (4)$$

The required correlation difference for significance at the 5 percent level under this sample design is $1.96 \times 0.677 = 1.33$ correlation units. The 2019 paper's evidence was therefore even further from the significance threshold than the 2026 paper's evidence. Correlation changes would have needed to move across nearly the entire possible range (from $+0.65$ to -0.65 , or wider) to clear the test for indicators centred around zero.

The 2019 paper did not report Fisher tests on its correlation changes. It reported the pre-and-post comparison visually in Figure 1 and interpreted the scatter as evidence of breakdown. The statistical procedure that would have been required to validate that interpretation was not applied, and would not have supported the headline "11 of 17" framing the paper draws from it, had it been.

5.5 Applying the Fisher test to the 2019 paper's indicators

Although the 2019 paper does not report significance tests, the test can be applied directly to the correlations the paper presents. Table 4 reports the result for each of eighteen indicators from Figure 1 of the 2019 paper for which both the pre-2011 and post-2011 correlations are available. The pre-period is 2001-02 to 2011-12 ($n_1 = 11$); the post-period is 2012-13 to 2017-18 ($n_2 = 6$); the standard error is the 0.677 derived above.

Table 4: Fisher r-to-z test applied to eighteen indicators from Subramanian (2019), Figure 1

Indicator	r_1 (2001-11)	r_2 (2012-17)	z -stat	p -value	Sig. at 5%?
IIP Manufacturing	+0.70	-0.78	2.825	0.005	Yes
IIP Consumer goods	+0.72	-0.71	2.651	0.008	Yes
Steel	+0.84	-0.32	2.294	0.022	Yes
Exports GS	+0.04	-0.86	1.970	0.049	Yes
Petroleum	-0.55	+0.56	-1.848	0.065	No (sig at 10%)
IIP-GVA Manufacturing	+0.68	-0.15	1.448	0.148	No
Tractor	+0.62	-0.21	1.386	0.166	No
IIP (Overall)	+0.70	+0.16	1.043	0.297	No
Cement	+0.23	-0.38	0.937	0.349	No
Railway Freight	+0.45	-0.13	0.909	0.363	No
Imports GS	+0.16	-0.36	0.795	0.426	No
Foreign Tourist	+0.67	+0.28	0.773	0.440	No
Commercial Vehicles	+0.50	+0.69	-0.441	0.659	No
Airlines	+0.80	+0.88	-0.409	0.682	No
Credit (overall)	+0.19	+0.03	0.24	0.8105	No
Credit (Industry)	+0.10	-0.48	0.921	0.3572	No
2-Wheeler sales	+0.08	-0.05	0.192	0.847	No
Electricity	+0.58	+0.55	0.065	0.948	No

Four of eighteen indicators show statistically significant correlation change at the 5 percent level: IIP Manufacturing, IIP Consumer goods, Exports (GS) and Steel. One more, Petroleum, clears the 10 percent threshold. The remaining thirteen changes, including IIP-GVA Manufacturing, Tractor, IIP (Overall), Credit (Industry), Cement, Railway Freight, Imports GS, Foreign Tourist, Commercial Vehicles, Airlines, Credit (overall), 2-Wheeler sales, and Electricity, do not differ from the pre-period correlation at conventional significance levels. The 2019 paper's headline that "11 of 17 indicators turned negatively correlated with GDP" counts dot positions on the y-axis of Figure 1 and treats each as evidence; the Fisher test shows that for fourteen of the eighteen testable cases, the move from positive to negative correlation could plausibly be a small-sample artifact rather than a real change.

The significant cases require separate treatment. In each, the change is statistically real at the sample sizes used; the question is what the change is real evidence *of*. The 2019 paper attributes such changes to the 2015 GDP methodology revision. Two facts cut against that attribution.

First, all four indicators significant at the 5 percent level reversed direction on the extended 2012 to 2024 window. Table 2 above documents the reversals: IIP Manufacturing has moved from -0.78 to +0.92, IIP Consumer goods from -0.71 to +0.82, Steel from -0.32 to +0.50, and Exports GS from -0.86 to +0.52 (Appendix B). A break induced by the 2015 methodology should persist; these breaks did not. They tracked the concentrated 2016 to 2019 shock period

(demonetization, GST, NBFC crisis) and dissipated as the post-period extended past those shocks. (Petroleum, the fifth indicator to clear the 10 percent threshold, shifted from -0.55 on 2001 to 2011 data to $+0.56$ on 2012 to 2017 data, and strengthens further positive to $+0.81$ on 2012 to 2024 data; the direction of its change is continuous across windows rather than reversing, and its correlation pattern does not support a methodology-break interpretation.)

Second, the four 5-percent-significant indicators are concentrated in oil-intensive and trade-exposed sectors (IIP Manufacturing, IIP Consumer goods, and Steel are oil-intensive; Exports GS is a trade series). The 2014 to 2016 oil price collapse (Brent fell from approximately \$100 to under \$30 per barrel) and the contemporaneous global trade slowdown affected these sectors directly. Their measured GDP elasticity could shift on a five-year window without the underlying GDP measurement methodology changing.

The combined implication is straightforward. The 2019 paper's correlation evidence rested on a headline count ("11 of 17") in which most of the underlying changes were not statistically significant at conventional thresholds. Of the four that were significant at 5 percent, all four have since reversed; the one additional indicator clearing the 10 percent threshold, Petroleum, also reversed sign on 2012 to 2017 data and strengthens further positive on extended data. The empirical foundation the 2019 paper built was either statistically empty (fourteen of eighteen cases at the 5 percent level) or window-specific to a shock period that has since passed (the significant cases that reversed). The 2026 paper carries the qualitative framing of this evidence forward without applying the test that would distinguish its components, and without reporting that the indicators on which the 2019 case actually had statistical traction now point in the opposite direction.

5.6 The precision the magnitude claim requires exceeds what the data can support

The 2026 paper reports an overestimation of 1.5 to 1.9 percentage points per year, a range of 0.4 percentage points. The evidentiary basis for this precision, on the correlation side, consists of five correlation changes whose 95 percent confidence intervals individually span approximately 1.0 to 1.5 correlation units (see Section 4.2 above). The statistical imprecision of the inputs is an order of magnitude larger than the claimed precision of the output.

The 2026 paper's informal sector contribution of 0.4 to 0.8 pp (Section 3) and its deflator-wedge contribution of approximately 1 pp (Section 4) are added to produce the headline range. Each input is independently weak: the correlation evidence is not significant, the informal sector gap is computed across non-comparable surveys, the deflator wedge is an accounting artifact of the deflator selection. The paper treats these as independent corroborating pieces of evidence. Under any standard treatment of aggregate uncertainty across noisy independent estimates, the combined uncertainty is wider than the uncertainty of any individual component, not narrower. The paper's presentation inverts this: the aggregate range (1.5 to 1.9 pp, width 0.4 pp) is narrower than the individual component ranges, and substantially narrower than what the correlation evidence alone would admit.

An additional specification problem compounds the small-sample issue. The Fisher r -to- z test compares correlations across two periods under the assumption that the underlying relationship is stable except for the effect being tested. In the AFS application, the effect being tested is whether the 2015 methodology revision changed the indicator-GDP relationship. The test is valid only if the alternative source of correlation change, namely structural transition of the Indian economy, can be ruled out. It cannot. Over the 1995 to 2024 window the test spans, digital payment adoption, GST-driven formalization, falling oil intensity of output, rising services share, and public capex expansion all shift the elasticities that the correlations measure. The test therefore cannot distinguish methodology-induced correlation change from economy-induced correlation change. At the sample sizes available, it also cannot distinguish either from noise. The correlation evidence is therefore triply unidentified: under-powered statistically, non-unique in interpretation, and fragile to individual observations.

5.7 Serial correlation and window sensitivity

Two further problems compound the small-sample issue.

First, macroeconomic growth rates are serially correlated. Observations in adjacent years are not independent. Under standard adjustments for first-order autocorrelation, the effective sample size is smaller than the nominal count of annual observations. The direction of this adjustment is unambiguous: effective n shrinks, standard errors rise, required correlation differences for significance rise. The AFS correlations, which do not clear significance at nominal sample sizes, move further from significance under any reasonable autocorrelation adjustment. The four 2019-paper indicators that clear significance at nominal n are closer to the threshold under autocorrelation correction; IIP Manufacturing and IIP Consumer goods (with p -values of 0.005 and 0.008) likely survive, while Steel ($p = 0.022$) and Exports GS ($p = 0.049$) would tighten further and may fall below conventional thresholds.

Second, the 2026 paper's choice of 2011 to 2012 as the structural break point is not supported by the data as the location of the strongest break. [Singh and Sinha \(2026\)](#) report Chow-type structural break F-statistics across ten candidate break years from FY2007-08 to FY2016-17. For several of the five indicator pairs, FY2007-08 or FY2008-09 produces a stronger break statistic than FY2011-12. For others, no candidate year clears conventional significance thresholds. The data do not identify 2011-12 as where the structural break occurs. The choice of that year as the break point is an assumption imposed on the data by the 2026 paper (and the 2019 paper before it), not an empirical finding extracted from them.

5.8 Combined implication

Across six dimensions, the correlation evidence in the 2026 paper does not support what the paper asks it to carry. The five correlation changes in the 2026 paper are not statistically significant at standard thresholds. The individual period correlations have confidence intervals wide enough to include negative values. The correlations reverse sign on single-observation

perturbations. Of the eighteen testable correlation changes in the 2019 paper, fourteen are statistically indistinguishable from sampling noise; the four that are significant have since reversed on extended data. The precision of the headline magnitude claim exceeds the precision of the underlying inputs by an order of magnitude. The specific break year on which the entire pre-and-post framework rests is not identified by the data.

The correlation evidence is the empirical spine of both papers. For the 2026 paper, that spine is statistically indistinguishable from noise at the sample sizes used. For the 2019 paper, four of eighteen correlation changes were statistically real at the time of publication; all four have since reversed, leaving the qualitative claim that the 2019 paper drew from them without persistent empirical support.

6 Seven Years of Reversals: Same Conclusion, Different Evidence

6.1 A research program with a fixed conclusion

The 2019 paper and the 2026 paper share a headline claim: Indian GDP growth has been overstated since 2011. The lead author of the 2019 paper is a co-author of the 2026 paper. The 2019 paper is cited in the 2026 paper's reference list. The 2026 paper is the continuation of the 2019 paper under additional authorship and with seven years of additional data.

Across those seven years, five specific positions on which the 2019 paper's claim rested have been reversed in the 2026 paper. The overall magnitude has fallen. The mechanisms used to derive the magnitude have changed. The indicators used to establish the empirical breakdown have changed. The 2026 paper does not acknowledge these reversals. It presents a substantially different empirical case as though it were a continuation and refinement of the 2019 case. Each reversal is documentable with direct quotations and page references; the full quotations are collected in [Appendix A](#).

6.2 Reversal 1: Double deflation

The 2019 paper stated that the absence of double deflation “immediately induces a bias” ([Subramanian, 2019](#), p. 19). Table 3 of the 2019 paper was constructed to demonstrate the bias. The mechanism was used to derive approximately 1 percentage point of the 2019 paper's claimed 2.5 pp overestimation. The 2026 paper states that the absence of double deflation was “a relatively minor problem” ([Anand et al., 2026](#), p. 3) and that “double deflation per se is not the solution to this problem” ([Anand et al., 2026](#), p. 15, n. 18). The 2026 paper's Table 3 is constructed to demonstrate the opposite of what the 2019 Table 3 demonstrated.

The 1 percentage point the 2019 paper attributed to this mechanism is not accounted for in the 2026 decomposition. [Section 4](#) develops the full reversal.

6.3 Reversal 2: Informal sector

The 2019 paper addressed informal activity narrowly, through informal manufacturing. It stated that informal manufacturing “accounts for 30 percent of manufacturing GVA and hence about 5 percent of overall GVA” (Subramanian, 2019, p. 25), and that informal-sector proxy problems arising from demonetization and GST were “not an explanation for our results because our baseline results do not cover the period beyond March 2017” (Subramanian, 2019, p. 26). The 2019 framework therefore treated informal activity as a small channel and confined the baseline sample to a period that predated the major informal-sector shocks.

The 2026 paper takes a different object. It treats the entire informal or unorganized economy, reported at approximately 44 percent of GVA (Anand et al., 2026, p. 10), as a primary channel and attributes 0.4 to 0.8 pp of the 1.5 to 1.9 pp total overestimation to informal sector mismeasurement across a full 2015 to 2023 window (Anand et al., 2026, p. 20). The scope, weight, and sample window of the informal-sector channel have all expanded without the 2019 framing being reconciled. A narrowly-scoped, small-weight, pre-shock channel in 2019 becomes a broadly-scoped, primary-weight, full-period channel in 2026. Section 3 develops why the 0.4 to 0.8 pp estimate is not extractable from the data even on its own terms.

6.4 Reversal 3: Tax indicators

The 2019 paper stated: “We do not use tax indicators because of the major changes in direct and indirect taxes in the post-2011 period which render the tax-to-GDP relationship different and unstable, and hence make the indicators unreliable proxies for GDP growth” (Subramanian, 2019, p. 6). The 2026 paper uses direct tax revenues as one of its six headline macro indicators (Anand et al., 2026, p. 4). The 2019 objection is not addressed.

When post-2020 tax behaviour contradicts the overestimation thesis, the 2026 paper introduces a dedicated Appendix C to explain the tax boom as composition-driven rather than growth-driven. A variable ruled unreliable in 2019 is promoted to headline evidence in 2026 when it supports the slowdown, then walled off in an appendix when it contradicts the thesis. Section 7 develops why the composition argument fails on its own terms.

6.5 Reversal 4: Magnitude

The 2019 paper estimated overestimation at approximately 2.5 pp per year, with a 95 percent confidence interval of 1.5 to 3.5 pp (Subramanian, 2019, p. 17). The 2026 paper estimates 1.5 to 1.9 pp per year (Anand et al., 2026, p. 20). The 2026 range sits entirely within the lower half of the 2019 paper’s 95 percent confidence interval, with its lower end coinciding with the 2019 lower bound.

The two estimates are drawn from different samples and rest on different mechanisms, so the fact that the 2026 range lies within the 2019 confidence interval does not by itself constitute a formal statistical inconsistency. What the shift from a central estimate of 2.5 pp to a range of

1.5 to 1.9 pp does constitute is a reconciliation failure. The 2026 paper presents its estimate as a refinement of the 2019 estimate, but does not indicate which components of the 1 percentage point reduction in the central estimate correspond to which mechanisms that have been abandoned or replaced from the 2019 decomposition. Without that reconciliation, a reader cannot assess whether the 2026 revision reflects improved measurement, reweighting of mechanisms, or simple magnitude compression under a different evidence base. The 2019 paper's 1 pp attributed to double deflation is not accounted for; the correlation-breakdown contribution is not reassessed despite the indicators having failed to replicate; the cross-country regression coefficient has shifted. A reader is left to assume continuity between the two estimates where the underlying derivations do not support it.

6.6 Reversal 5: Indicator set

The 2019 paper used 17 macro indicators and reported that 11 had turned negatively correlated with GDP after 2011 (Subramanian, 2019, p. 7). The 2026 paper uses 6 macro indicators, 4 of which overlap with the 2019 set (Anand et al., 2026, p. 4). Thirteen indicators from the 2019 set are absent from the 2026 paper.

On extended 2012 to 2024 data, ten of the eleven indicators flagged as negatively correlated on 2012 to 2017 data show positive correlation. The 2026 paper does not report this. Section 5.5 establishes that the 2019 paper's correlation-breakdown count was largely composed of statistically insignificant changes at the time of publication, and that the four changes that were significant have since reversed. The 2026 paper has replaced the failing indicators rather than engaged with the failure.

6.7 The arithmetic does not reconcile

The 2019 paper's 2.5 pp overestimation was built from three named components: double deflation bias in formal manufacturing (approximately 1 pp), correlation breakdown across 17 macro indicators (substantial additional contribution), and cross-country regression evidence (the remaining contribution). The 2026 paper's 1.5 to 1.9 pp overestimation is built from two named components: informal sector mismeasurement (0.4 to 0.8 pp) and deflator-driven wedge in services and corporate sales (approximately 1 pp).

None of the 2026 components correspond to the 2019 components. The double deflation contribution is conceded to be minor, which removes 1 pp from the 2019 total. The correlation breakdown does not replicate, which removes the correlation-based contribution. The cross-country regression coefficient falls by 24 percent when Covid observations are added. If each of the 2019 components is revised in line with the 2026 paper's own treatment, the residual supported by the 2019 evidence is close to zero.

The 2026 claim of 1.5 to 1.9 pp is therefore not a refinement of the 2019 claim. It is a new claim built from substantially new components. The two papers are not cumulative; they offer two independent estimates based on two largely non-overlapping evidence bases. That the two

independent estimates are close in magnitude does not provide corroboration. It indicates that the conclusion has been held stable while the inputs have been replaced.

6.8 What the pattern establishes

Empirical research programs are expected to revise their claims as data accumulate. Revision is not the problem. The problem is the pattern of revision: mechanisms that supported the 2019 claim are abandoned without the 2019 claim being withdrawn, new mechanisms are introduced without the old ones being reconciled, and the headline conclusion is preserved across a complete turnover of underlying evidence.

This pattern is inconsistent with the confidence with which either the 2019 or the 2026 magnitude claim has been asserted. A claim whose supporting evidence has been replaced five times in seven years, while the claim itself remains stable to within a narrow decimal range, is a claim anchored in its conclusion rather than derived from its inputs. The 2026 paper does not present it as such. The cumulative record establishes that it is.

7 Tax Revenue: The 2026 Paper's Own Evidence Contradicts Its Thesis

7.1 The post-2020 tax performance

Table 5 reproduces the 2026 paper's own tax revenue figures from Table C.1 on page 26 of the paper.

Table 5: Average annual growth rates, tax revenue and GDP. Source: AFS 2026, Table C.1, p. 26

Item	2004 to 2011	2011 to 2019	2019 to 2024	2011 to 2024
Oil tax	10.6	12.3	5.8	9.7
Nonoil tax	18.1	10.3	14.9	12.1
Total tax	16.8	10.6	13.7	11.8
Nominal GDP	15.5	11.0	10.5	10.8
Real GDP	6.9	6.6	5.3	6.1

Tax buoyancy (nonoil tax growth divided by nominal GDP growth) by sub-period:

- 2004 to 2011: 1.17
- 2011 to 2019: 0.94
- 2019 to 2024: **1.42**
- Full period 2011 to 2024: 1.12

The 2019 to 2024 buoyancy of 1.42 is the highest of the four sub-periods, exceeding even the 2004 to 2011 period (which the 2026 paper treats as the boom years it argues were underestimated).

The tax-to-GDP ratio, shown in AFS Figure C.1 on page 27, moves from approximately 16.5 percent (stable over 2004 to 2022) to approximately 18.6 percent by 2024. A 2 percentage point jump in two years.

7.2 The problem with attributing tax growth to composition rather than growth

The 2026 paper's Appendix C argues that the post-2020 tax boom reflects "changes in the composition of consumption, not because growth was exceptionally strong" (Anand et al., 2026, p. 28). The appendix documents three specific channels: the surge in high-income filers (those above Rs. 1 crore rising from approximately 8 percent to 18 percent of total reported income), the rapid expansion of Global Capability Centers (GCCs) generating professional employment, and the boom in SUV sales and high-slab GST items.

Each of these channels describes real economic activity. GCC expansion generates services output: office leases, technology procurement, payroll, and vendor payments, all of which enter GDP through the services components of GVA. SUV sales are recorded in manufacturing output, dealer margins in trade services, vehicle financing in financial services, and the GST collected on them in indirect taxes. Real estate transactions generate construction GVA, stamp duty revenue, and financial intermediation. The surge in high-income filers reflects professional and capital incomes that are themselves components of the income side of national accounts.

The composition argument therefore describes a pattern of economic activity that should appear in measured GDP. If GCCs expanded, services GVA should reflect it. If SUV sales surged, manufacturing and trade GVA should reflect it. If real estate boomed, construction and financial services GVA should reflect it. The 2026 paper treats these activities as explaining why tax revenue grew independently of GDP growth. But these activities are GDP growth. They are not a separate phenomenon that can be invoked to explain away the tax-GDP relationship; they are the tax-GDP relationship.

The paper's framing implicitly requires that the activities generating the tax boom occurred in sectors or forms that the GDP methodology fails to capture. Appendix C does not make this argument. It does not identify which of the tax-generating activities are missing from measured GVA or explain the mechanism through which GCC output, SUV production, or real estate transactions would be excluded from national accounts. In the absence of such an argument, the composition evidence in Appendix C is evidence for GDP growth in the sectors the appendix describes, not evidence against it.

7.3 The K-shaped recovery argument does not rescue the thesis

Appendix C invokes the K-shaped nature of the post-Covid recovery to argue that growth was concentrated in heavily taxed segments while the broader economy remained weak. This is a coherent description of distributional dynamics. It does not, however, support the claim that aggregate GDP was overstated.

A K-shaped recovery is one in which some sectors or income groups grow rapidly while others stagnate or contract. The aggregate growth rate is the weighted average of the two arms of the K. If the upper arm (high-income professionals, luxury consumption, formal corporate profits) grew rapidly enough to generate 14.9 percent nonoil tax growth, that growth enters the aggregate. If the lower arm (informal enterprises, low-income households, rural consumption) stagnated, that stagnation also enters the aggregate. The resulting aggregate may be lower than if both arms had grown, but it is not lower than the weighted combination of the two.

The 2026 paper's informal sector argument (Section 3) claims that the lower arm of the K was growing at 6.8 percent nominal rather than the 10.0 percent attributed by the national accounts. Even accepting this claim, the upper arm of the K, which Appendix C documents as generating surging professional incomes, luxury consumption, and real estate activity, would need to be growing at correspondingly higher rates to produce the observed tax revenue. The paper does not reconcile the two arms. It uses the weak lower arm (informal sector) to argue that aggregate GDP is overstated, while simultaneously documenting a strong upper arm (taxable income and consumption) that should partially offset the informal sector drag in any weighted aggregate.

The K-shaped framing therefore cuts in both directions. It supports the claim that the informal sector may have underperformed formal-sector proxies. It simultaneously establishes that the formal and high-income segments were generating substantial real economic activity. The 2026 paper uses the first implication to mark down GDP and walls off the second implication in an appendix. A consistent treatment would net the two: informal sector underperformance reduces the aggregate while formal and high-income sector outperformance raises it. Appendix C does not perform this netting. It presents the strong performance of the taxable economy as a compositional curiosity rather than as a component of aggregate output.

7.4 The structural transformation of Indian tax administration

The 2026 paper's use of tax revenue as a macro indicator rests on an unstated assumption: that the tax-to-GDP relationship is sufficiently stable over 2011 to 2024 for tax revenue growth to proxy aggregate GDP growth. The 2019 paper explicitly rejected this assumption and excluded tax indicators. The 2026 paper does not engage the 2019 paper's rejection. Nor does it engage what has happened to Indian tax administration since 2017.

Between 2017 and 2024 India implemented a sequence of structural changes to tax administration that systematically expanded the visible tax base:

- GST rollout in July 2017 pulled previously informal transactions into the formal tax net.
- E-invoicing under GST was phased in for progressively smaller businesses, reaching enterprises with turnover above Rs. 5 crore by 2022.
- GSTN-income tax data matching flagged inconsistencies between GST filings and income tax returns automatically.
- Mandatory PAN-Aadhaar linkage expanded the identifiable taxpayer base.

- Form 26AS and the Annual Information Statement (AIS) cross-reference income across sources (TDS, SFT, mutual fund transactions, foreign remittances) for each filer.
- TDS scope was expanded to new transaction categories including e-commerce, rent above specified thresholds, and cash withdrawals.
- Faceless assessment and scrutiny expanded under CBDT.

Each of these changes expands the tax base through administrative detection, not through aggregate economic growth. Under their operation, tax revenue can rise even when the underlying economy grows at trend or below. The 14.9 percent nonoil tax revenue growth over 2019 to 2024 therefore reflects three components: genuine economic activity, composition shifts toward heavily taxed categories, and administrative expansion of the visible base. The 2026 paper's Appendix C engages the first two. It does not engage the third.

The consequence for the AFS thesis is not a specific quantitative adjustment. It is structural. Tax revenue growth over a period of active tax-base formalization cannot be used as a clean proxy for aggregate economic activity. The tax-to-GDP elasticity that would license such use is unlikely to be stable across the 2011 to 2024 window, because the denominator of that elasticity (the fraction of aggregate activity visible to the tax system) is itself rising over the period.

This is a specification problem, not a magnitude debate. The AFS framework cannot use tax as a macro indicator and simultaneously hold that tax buoyancy reflects composition or compliance effects rather than aggregate growth. Either tax is a clean proxy (in which case the 14.9 percent growth over 2019 to 2024 contradicts the overestimation thesis on the arithmetic developed above), or tax is not a clean proxy (in which case tax revenue growth contains information that does not cleanly separate aggregate GDP change from base-broadening). In neither case does the tax evidence support the 2026 paper's magnitude claim. In the first case it contradicts it directly. In the second case it is silent.

The 2026 paper has placed tax revenue among its six headline indicators. It has built Appendix C to explain the post-2020 tax boom. It has not established that tax revenue is an appropriate indicator for the question the paper is asking.

8 Discussion: What the Cumulative Evidence Establishes

8.1 The six findings in summary

Sections 2 through 7 establish six independent findings, each verifiable against the 2019 and 2026 papers and against public data. Each is sufficient on its own to materially weaken the paper's magnitude claim:

1. The 2019 paper's correlation-breakdown finding does not survive extension of the data window, as Section 2 documents. IIP Manufacturing has moved from -0.78 to $+0.92$.

2. The informal sector contribution of 0.4 to 0.8 pp is an assumption range layered on non-comparable surveys (UNES to ASUSE, spanning thirteen years), not a measurement.
3. The sales-GVA wedge is partly an accounting consequence of the CPI core-for-sales, WPI-for-GVA deflator asymmetry the paper itself creates. The use of CPI core rather than headline CPI reduces the mechanical component, but a portion of the reported wedge remains attributable to deflator divergence rather than to real mismeasurement.
4. No correlation change in Figure 2 reaches statistical significance. Of eighteen testable changes in the 2019 paper, fourteen are statistically indistinguishable from noise; the four that clear significance have since reversed.
5. Five specific 2019 positions are reversed in the 2026 paper without acknowledgment. The 2026 magnitude range sits entirely within the lower half of the 2019 paper's 95 percent confidence interval without reconciliation.
6. The 2026 paper's own tax appendix documents surging economic activity in taxable segments (high-income professional employment, luxury consumption, real estate, formal corporate profits) while characterising this activity as compositional rather than as growth. These activities are components of GDP. The paper does not reconcile the strong performance it documents in taxable sectors with its claim that aggregate GDP was overstated.

8.2 The findings are not substitutable

Each finding targets a different component of the 2026 paper's case: the indicator evidence, the informal sector channel, the sales-GVA wedge, the Figure 2 correlations, the 2019-to-2026 relationship, and the tax appendix. They do not overlap. Because different components support different portions of the headline claim (informal sector supplies 0.4 to 0.8 pp, deflator wedge supplies approximately 1 pp, correlation evidence supplies the qualitative framing, cross-country regression supplies one of two magnitude derivations), the headline claim cannot be preserved by conceding part of the critique and retaining the rest. Each component is independently weakened.

8.3 The framework assumes an economy that has not changed

The 2019 and 2026 papers share an implicit assumption: that indicator-GDP relationships are sufficiently stable across 2001 to 2024 that observed changes constitute evidence of measurement failure. Under this assumption, any change in indicator-GDP correlation is attributed to the 2015 methodology. The possibility that underlying elasticities are changing because the Indian economy is undergoing structural transition is not engaged.

Post-2011 India is not a stationary economy. Several structural shifts operate over the period covered:

1. **Digitization of payments and transactions.** UPI was launched in 2016 and has scaled

from negligible to a dominant share of retail transactions by 2024, shifting the visibility and velocity of economic activity in ways that do not map onto pre-2016 proxies.

2. **Formalization under GST.** The July 2017 GST rollout pulled previously informal transactions into the formal tax net, mechanically shifting the relationship between formal-sector indicators (IIP, corporate sales, tax revenue) and aggregate GDP as the measured formal share rises.
3. **Falling oil intensity of output.** Crude oil consumption per unit of real GDP has declined. Elasticities estimated on 2001 to 2011 data over-attribute petroleum growth to GDP growth thereafter.
4. **Declining logistics costs and freight intensity.** Logistics cost as a share of GDP is widely cited as having declined materially over this period, driven by road and rail infrastructure investment. Freight tonnage per unit of GDP is not constant.
5. **Compositional shift toward services and high-value manufacturing.** Services have risen from under 50 percent of GVA in 2001 toward over 55 percent by 2024 (MoSPI National Accounts Statistics). Steel and cement intensity per unit of GDP is structurally lower in a services-heavy economy.
6. **Public capital expenditure rising sharply.** Central government capex rose from approximately 1.6 percent of GDP in 2019 to approximately 3.2 percent by 2024. The composition of growth shifts, and pre-2011 proxy relationships do not capture this.
7. **Direct Benefit Transfer infrastructure.** DBT displaces leakage-prone subsidy channels, changing the household distribution of disposable income in ways that affect which consumption proxies track aggregate activity.
8. **Tax compliance infrastructure.** PAN-Aadhaar linkage, AIS, Form 26AS, expanded TDS, e-invoicing under GST, and GSTN data matching have expanded the visible tax base. Tax revenue growth therefore reflects detection as well as activity.

Each shift changes the elasticity between a specific macro indicator and aggregate GDP. A portion of what the AFS framework interprets as methodology-induced breakdown is consistent with the economic transformation Indian policy has been designed to produce.

Three implications follow. First, the indicator-correlation evidence cannot be read as a test of methodology in isolation; it conflates methodology change with economic transformation. Without a specification that separates these, the framework is under-identified. Second, the tax evidence in Section 7 becomes positively uninformative for the overestimation thesis, because the factors raising tax buoyancy post-2017 (formalization, compliance, digitization) are exactly the structural changes listed above. The AFS Appendix C composition argument implicitly invokes these structural factors; having invoked them, the paper cannot also treat tax as a clean macro proxy. Third, both papers test correlation stability against a null of methodology breakdown without testing against the null of economic transformation. Under standard inference, selecting one of two alternative explanations without testing against the other is assumption, not evidence.

The 2026 paper's framework therefore does not merely lack the precision to support 1.5 to 1.9 pp. It lacks the specification to distinguish methodology failure from structural change at all.

8.4 What the paper fails to do

The 2026 paper fails on standard obligations that empirical research owes its readers. It does not report what happened to the 2019 paper's headline finding on extended data. It does not apply significance tests to the correlation evidence on which its qualitative claims rest. It does not reconcile the arithmetic of its revised magnitude with the mechanisms it has abandoned from the 2019 paper. It does not address the fact that its own tax data, in its own appendix, point in the opposite direction from its thesis under the paper's own composition argument. It does not acknowledge that its 1.5 to 1.9 pp estimate sits entirely within the lower half of the 2019 paper's reported confidence interval. It does not distinguish between correlation changes induced by the 2015 methodology revision and correlation changes induced by the structural transformation of the Indian economy post-2011.

Each omission is not incidental. Each is an operation that responsible empirical research would perform before advancing a headline quantitative claim.

8.5 The magnitude claim is unsupported

The 2026 paper reports Indian GDP overstatement at 1.5 to 1.9 percentage points per year, with an implied level overstatement of 22 percent as of 2025. The evidence presented does not support these claims. The correlation evidence is statistically insignificant. The informal sector contribution is an assumption range across non-comparable surveys. The deflator wedge is partly an artifact of the asymmetric deflator choice (CPI core for sales, WPI-based indices for GVA), though its mechanical magnitude is smaller than headline CPI deflation would imply. The revised mechanisms do not reconcile with the 2019 paper's mechanisms. The tax data document vigorous activity in precisely the sectors (formal corporate, high-income services, luxury consumption) that should register in measured GDP, yet the paper treats this activity as a compositional curiosity rather than as evidence bearing on the aggregate. The framework cannot distinguish methodology failure from structural change.

This paper does not substitute an alternative magnitude; doing so would repeat the error the 2026 paper commits. The claim established here is negative and specific: the 2026 paper's magnitude of 1.5 to 1.9 pp is not empirically supported by the evidence the paper presents.

9 Conclusion

The 2026 Anand-Felman-Subramanian paper advances a specific quantitative claim: that Indian GDP growth has been overestimated by 1.5 to 1.9 percentage points per year since 2011, with a cumulative level overstatement of approximately 22 percent as of 2025. The paper has been

discussed in policy and media commentary at the level of its headline number. This paper has examined what the evidence behind that number actually shows.

The evidence does not support the claim. The 2019 paper's correlation-breakdown finding, which the 2026 paper carries forward as the qualitative motivation for its analysis, does not replicate on extended data. The informal sector contribution of 0.4 to 0.8 pp is derived from non-comparable surveys spanning thirteen years. The sales-GVA wedge that serves as independent evidence is partly generated by the paper's own deflator asymmetry (CPI core on the sales side, WPI-based indices on the GVA side), though the use of CPI core rather than headline CPI narrows the mechanical contribution. None of the five correlation changes in the paper's Figure 2 reaches statistical significance. Of the eighteen 2019-paper correlation changes the Fisher test can be applied to, fourteen are statistically indistinguishable from sampling noise; the four that are significant have all reversed on extended data. Five specific positions from the 2019 paper on which the 2026 thesis rests have been reversed without acknowledgment. The paper's own tax appendix documents surging professional incomes, luxury consumption, and formal corporate activity, then characterises these as composition effects rather than as evidence of GDP growth, even though the activities described are themselves components of national output.

The 2026 paper is the continuation of a research program that began with the 2019 Harvard working paper by the same lead author of that earlier work, and that now includes additional co-authors, one of whom was acknowledged in the 2019 paper. Across the seven years between the two papers, the headline claim of Indian GDP overestimation has remained stable within a narrow decimal range while the indicators, mechanisms, decomposition, and even the confidence interval supporting it have been substantially rebuilt. No individual revision in this sequence is illegitimate. The cumulative pattern, in which conclusions remain stable while supporting evidence is repeatedly replaced, is not how empirical research is supposed to function.

The February 2026 MoSPI methodological revision reflects serious engagement with technical concerns about Indian GDP estimation. Legitimate methodological critique of Indian national accounts exists and is being addressed through proper statistical channels. The 2026 paper is not part of that process. It is a paper that makes a sweeping quantitative claim, advances it with confidence, and has received policy and media attention commensurate with that confidence. The evidence behind the claim does not meet the standard that policy-influential empirical claims should have to meet. The findings documented in this paper establish that. Whether policy discussion will update on the evidence rather than on the headline is a separate question.

A Appendix A: Direct Quotations, 2019 vs 2026

This appendix provides verbatim quotations from the 2019 and 2026 papers, organised by the five reversal topics established in Section 6. All quotations are direct from the cited source. Page numbers refer to the working paper PDFs as published.

A.1 Double Deflation

The 2019 paper treats the absence of double deflation as a core mechanism producing approximately 1 percentage point of the claimed overestimation. The 2026 paper treats the same absence as “a relatively minor problem.”

Subramanian 2019, p. 19: “Ideally, if output values are deflated by output prices and input values by input prices (what is called ‘double deflation’), real value added can be properly estimated. But the methodology did not also involve a move to such double deflation; the methodology involved deflating both output and input values by output prices. This immediately induces a bias as the example below shows.”

AFS 2026, p. 3: “To be clear, the main problem with the 2015 series was not the absence of double deflation, as is often alleged. In fact, this was a relatively minor problem. The real problem was the use of inappropriate deflators and inappropriate indicators.”

AFS 2026, p. 14: “This result shows that the real problem is not the lack of double deflation. It is inappropriate deflators.”

AFS 2026, p. 15, footnote 18: “Double deflation per se is not the solution to this problem.”

A.2 Informal Sector

The 2019 paper addresses informal activity through informal manufacturing, which it reports at approximately 5 percent of overall GVA, and rules out informal-sector proxy problems as an explanation for its baseline results on the ground that the baseline sample ended in March 2017. The 2026 paper treats the broader informal or unorganized economy, reported at approximately 44 percent of GVA, as a primary mechanism accounting for 0.4 to 0.8 pp of the 1.5 to 1.9 pp overall claim across a 2015 to 2023 window. The scope, weight, and sample window of the informal-sector channel have all expanded without the 2019 framing being reconciled.

Subramanian 2019, p. 25: “The informal sector accounts for 30 percent of manufacturing GVA and hence about 5 percent of overall GVA.”

Subramanian 2019, p. 26: “This, however, is not an explanation for our results because our baseline results do not cover the period beyond March 2017 when the impacts of demonetization, and especially the GST, would have been most severe.”

AFS 2026, p. 10: “Far fewer data were available for the unorganized sector, however. And this was a serious drawback, since the sector accounts for roughly 44 percent of GVA.”

AFS 2026, p. 20: “Adjustments to informal sector nominal GVA account for an additional 0.4–0.8 percentage points, depending on the assumption made.”

A.3 Tax Indicators

The 2019 paper excludes tax indicators on the explicit ground that the post-2011 tax-to-GDP relationship is unstable. The 2026 paper uses tax as one of six headline macro indicators, then walls off the post-2020 data in Appendix C when it contradicts the thesis.

Subramanian 2019, p. 6: “We do not use tax indicators because of the major changes in direct and indirect taxes in the post-2011 period which render the tax-to-GDP relationship different and unstable, and hence make the indicators unreliable proxies for GDP growth.”

AFS 2026, p. 4: “We chose six: exports of goods and services, bank credit (excluding food credit), the index of industrial production (IIP), electricity, tax revenues, and corporate sales.”

AFS 2026, p. 28: “Taxes thus boomed because of changes in the composition of consumption, not because growth was exceptionally strong.”

A.4 Magnitude

The 2019 paper reports overestimation at 2.5 percentage points per year with a 95 percent confidence interval of 1.5 to 3.5 pp. The 2026 paper reports 1.5 to 1.9 pp. The 2026 range sits entirely within the lower half of the 2019 interval, with its lower end coinciding with the 2019 lower bound; the 2026 paper does not acknowledge or explain this.

Subramanian 2019, p. 2: “We estimate that actual growth may have been about $4\frac{1}{2}$ percent with a 95 percent confidence interval of $3\frac{1}{2}$ - $5\frac{1}{2}$ percent.”

Subramanian 2019, p. 17: “The central estimate of $2\frac{1}{2}$ percent comes with a 95 percent confidence band of about 1 percent.”

AFS 2026, p. 3: “Subsequent growth between 2012 and 2023 may have been overestimated by about $1\frac{1}{2}$ -2 percentage points.”

AFS 2026, p. 20: “In total, the revision amounts to 1.5–1.9 percentage points.”

A.5 Indicator Set

The 2019 paper’s headline empirical finding was that 11 of 17 macro indicators had turned negatively correlated with GDP after 2011. IIP Manufacturing specifically was called “bizarre.” On the extended 2012 to 2024 window, IIP Manufacturing correlates with GDP at +0.92. The 2026 paper uses 6 indicators, 4 overlapping with the 2019 set, and does not report what happened to the 13 dropped indicators on extended data.

Subramanian 2019, p. 7: “16 out of 17 indicators are positively correlated with GDP growth before 2011. . . . However, post-2011, 11 out of 17 indicators are negatively correlated with GDP.”

Subramanian 2019, p. 20: “Pre-2011, the correlation between formal manufacturing value added growth and IIP manufacturing growth. . . is high and positive (0.7); post-2011, it turns negative (-0.1). This is bizarre.”

AFS 2026, p. 4: “We chose six: exports of goods and services, bank credit (excluding food credit), the index of industrial production (IIP), electricity, tax revenues, and corporate sales.”

No passage in the 2026 paper addresses what happened to the 13 indicators from the 2019 set that are absent from the 2026 analysis.

B Appendix B: Correlation Data, 2012 to 2024

Table 6 reports Pearson correlation coefficients between 17 macro indicators and two alternative GVA series (one excluding agriculture and public administration to match the AFS comparisons involving corporate sales, the second being headline GDP, 2011-12 base), computed on annual year-on-year growth rates over FY 2012-13 to FY 2024-25 ($n = 13$, including Covid years). In the column labels below, “GVA (excl. agri. and public admin.)” denotes the restricted series.

Table 6: Correlations with GVA (excluding agriculture and public administration) and with GDP, 2012 to 2024 ($n = 13$)

Indicator	Correlation with GVA	Correlation with GDP
Cement (000 tons)	+0.759	+0.759
Steel (000 tons)	+0.497	+0.499
Petroleum consumption (000 tons)	+0.823	+0.813
Airlines (passengers)	+0.763	+0.821
Commercial Vehicles (sales)	+0.562	+0.553
Revenue Earning Freight Traffic ¹	+0.400	+0.370
Electricity consumption ²	+0.847	+0.87
Tractor production	-0.454	-0.383
Foreign Tourist Arrivals	+0.481	+0.502
Imports (real)	+0.54	+0.608
Exports (real)	+0.49	+0.52
Credit	+0.47	+0.508
Credit (Ind.)	+0.313	+0.274
2-Wheeler sales	+0.581	+0.625
IIP Consumer (2011 base)	+0.816	+0.824
IIP Manufacturing (2011 base)	+0.908	+0.921
IIP Overall (2011 base)	+0.92	+0.936

Sixteen of seventeen indicators show positive correlation with both series. Only Tractor shows negative correlation, a pattern driven by agricultural cycle dynamics and unrelated to aggregate GDP. Seven indicators correlate above 0.70 with the restricted-GVA series: Cement, Petroleum, Airlines, Electricity, IIP Consumer, IIP Manufacturing and IIP (Overall). IIP Manufacturing

¹Railway freight data combine two Ministry of Railways series: Total Freight Loading (Revenue Earning plus non-revenue departmental traffic) for FY2011-12 through FY2017-18, and Revenue Earning Freight Traffic only for FY2018-19 onwards. The Total Freight Loading series is not published by the Ministry of Railways from FY2018-19 onwards.

²Electricity consumption growth rates are taken from the AFS (2026) replication data package, which sources the series from Table 6.8 (“Yearwise Consumption of Electricity—Sectorwise”) of MoSPI’s *Energy Statistics India* annual publication, originally compiled by the Central Electricity Authority (CEA). Growth rates computed from the MoSPI 2024 edition (which reports provisional 2022–23 data) match the AFS replication data exactly for FY2012-13 through FY2021-22. For FY2022-23, the MoSPI 2024 edition reports provisional growth of 6.58 percent, while the AFS data reports 9.38 percent, consistent with a subsequent data revision or the use of a broader CEA consumption definition in the final data.

correlates at +0.91 with the restricted-GVA series. The 2019 paper’s claim that this correlation had turned “bizarrely” negative post-2011 does not hold on extended data.

Data sources: CMIE Economic Outlook for most indicators; Ministry of Railways for freight loading (2018 to 2024 extension); RBI for credit; MoSPI for IIP and GDP series; WDI for imports and exports (GS). Electricity consumption growth rates are from the AFS (2026) replication data package, sourced from MoSPI *Energy Statistics India*, Table 6.8 (see footnote 2 above). Growth rates computed as annual year-on-year percentage changes.

C Appendix C: On Indicator Window Sensitivity

The differences between the 2019 paper’s reported correlations (computed over 2012 to 2017) and the 2012 to 2024 correlations reported in this paper invite a question: whether the reversal reflects a change in the underlying relationship or simply window extension past the 2016 to 2019 shock period.

A defender of the 2019 paper could argue that the 2012 to 2017 correlations were correct for that specific window, which captured demonetization, the GST transition, and the onset of the NBFC crisis. The defence is insufficient for the 2026 paper’s purposes for two reasons.

First, the 2026 paper does not claim overestimation only for 2012 to 2017. It claims 1.5 to 1.9 pp of annual overestimation over 2011 to 2023. If the 2012 to 2017 window captured unusual shock-period weakness that the post-2020 data has reversed, the full-period claim cannot be anchored in the pattern specific to the shock window. Extending the window to 2012 to 2024 is the correct test for a full-period claim, and the test fails.

Second, the 2019 paper itself presented its correlation finding as evidence of a structural break induced by the 2015 methodology revision, not as a cyclical phenomenon tied to specific post-2016 shocks. A structural break induced by methodology would persist. A shock-period phenomenon would not. The reversal of the correlations on extended data is therefore direct evidence against the structural-break interpretation that both the 2019 and 2026 papers rely on.

The 2026 paper is extrapolating from a shock-period pattern (2012 to 2017) to a full-period claim (2011 to 2023) without testing whether the shock-period pattern persists. Appendix B documents that it does not.

D Appendix D: Indicator vs GDP Growth Rate Comparison (2012–24)

Figure 2: Two-wheeler sales

Figure 3: Commercial Vehicles (sales)

Figure 4: Electricity Consumption

Figure 5: Railway Freight Load

Figure 6: IIP Manufacturing

Figure 7: IIP Cons.

Figure 8: Imports (Real)

Figure 9: Exports (Real)

Figure 10: Tourist Arrivals (For.)

Figure 11: Tractor Production

Figure 12: Petroleum Consumption

Figure 13: Cement Production

Figure 14: Bank Credit

Figure 15: Airline Passengers

Figure 16: Steel Production

Figure 17: IIP (Overall)

Figure 18: Real Credit to Industry

E Appendix E: Correlation Analysis of Indicators vs GVA & GDP Growth Rates (2012–24)

Figure 19: Two-wheeler sales

Figure 20: Commercial Vehicles (sales)

Figure 21: Electricity Consumption

Figure 22: Railway Freight Load

Figure 23: IIP Manufacturing

Figure 24: IIP Cons.

Figure 25: Imports (Real)

Figure 26: Exports (Real)

Figure 27: Tourist Arrivals (For.)

Figure 28: Tractor Production

Figure 29: Petroleum Consumption

Figure 30: Cement Production

Figure 31: Bank Credit

Figure 32: Airline Passengers

Figure 33: Steel Production

Figure 34: IIP (Overall)

Figure 35: Real Credit to Industry

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